

PURSUING PERFECTION: HARNESSING LEAN PRINCIPLES AND AGILE PRACTICES FOR EXCELLENCE

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ABSTRACT

The study explored Lean Manufacturing Adoption in a Wireless Equipment Manufacturing and Networking Services Organization. In this study a Simulation-Based Analysis was used. The term "Lean Manufacturing" (LM) is widely recognized and resonates globally in various business environments, particularly within manufacturing industries. While many organizations are still working towards successfully embracing lean practices, the awareness of Lean Management (LM) is prevalent. This paper delves into the journey of adopting lean manufacturing principles in an organization specializing in the manufacturing of wireless equipment and providing networking services. The study utilized simulation techniques to analyse the data. Motivated by the desire to revolutionize their supply chain and production system, the organization implemented lean management strategies. This involved leveraging the knowledge base and creativity of individual workers, reducing batch sizes, implementing Just-In-Time (JIT) production and inventory control, and accelerating cycle times. The focus was on discerning the distinction between value-creating activities and waste to foster quality from within.

The paper concludes by emphasizing the adaptation of lean principles to the entrepreneurial context, suggesting that entrepreneurs should evaluate progress differently from other types of ventures. In manufacturing, progress is traditionally measured by the production of high-quality physical goods. The paper encourages organizations to assess their current business processes, identifying opportunities to implement LM principles and improve overall business performance.

Keywords: Lean Manufacturing, Simulation, Waste, Just-In Time, Cycle Time, Inventory.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This case study delves into Warex India, an anonymized Indian organization situated in the North-eastern region, specializing in the production of wireless networking devices. Boasting a history of expansion and a diverse clientele, Warex India is actively involved in the specialized production and service delivery of wired and wireless networking solutions, networking security, and WAN optimization.

The company encounters challenges in managing a intricate supply chain network while catering to customers across the region. Operating primarily in a Make to Order environment, Warex India utilizes forecasting models for spare parts, driven by its customer support division. Additionally, the organization grapples with extended lead times for crucial components, presenting difficulties in monitoring and control.

The potential solution to effectively address Warex India's expansion goals and tackle long-term project enhancements lies in the implementation of Lean Management principles. Stemming from the lean manufacturing revolution, Lean thinking has transformed global supply chain and production systems. Its fundamental principles include tapping into the knowledge and creativity of individual workers, minimizing batch sizes, adopting Just-In-Time production and inventory control, and accelerating cycle times.

Entrepreneurs often exhibit reluctance to embrace traditional management practices early on, fearing bureaucratic hurdles and creativity constraints. However, Lean Management presents an alternative perspective, advocating for a customer-centric focus and continuous improvement in key processes. The lean organization, tailored to the entrepreneurial context, proposes measuring progress through validated learning instead of conventional metrics, underscoring a commitment to customer satisfaction.

A comprehensive entrepreneurship theory should encompass various facets of an early-stage venture, spanning vision and concept, product development, marketing and sales, scaling up, partnerships and distribution, as well as structure and organization design. Lean thinking, as a set of practices, serves as a guide for entrepreneurs in constructing successful organizations, emphasizing understanding customer value, optimizing value streams, and minimizing waste. The ultimate aim is to deliver impeccable value to customers through streamlined processes, cost reduction, and high-quality outputs.

Embracing Lean Management could empower Warex India to simplify information management, swiftly adapt to evolving customer preferences, and achieve a balance between variety, cost-effectiveness, and rapid throughput times. This case study posits that the adoption of Lean Management principles has the potential to pave the way for Warex India's sustained success in the wireless networking industry.

2. LEAN FOR GOODS AND SERVICES

A prevalent misconception suggests that lean principles are exclusively applicable to manufacturing, but this notion is inaccurate. Lean is a versatile approach that extends to all

businesses and processes. It transcends being a mere tactic or a cost-cutting initiative; instead, it represents a mindset and a mode of operation for an entire organization.

Businesses across diverse industries and service sectors, including healthcare and governments, are embracing lean principles as integral to their mindset and operations. Some organizations opt not to explicitly use the term "lean" but prefer to label their approach as a unique system. This choice emphasizes that lean is more than a temporary cost-cutting measure; it embodies the fundamental operational ethos of the company. The terminology "transformation" or "lean transformation" is frequently employed to describe a company's shift from conventional thinking to adopting lean principles. Such a shift necessitates a comprehensive transformation in how a company conducts its business, requiring a long-term perspective and unwavering perseverance.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In the past 8 years, Warex India has undergone substantial growth, accompanied by heightened demand. However, their existing processes are struggling to accommodate the surge in customer requirements. This increased demand has led to several organizational challenges, as outlined below:

- A) Inadequate visibility of materials
- B) Limited control over materials
- C) Inefficient material flow patterns
- D) Material losses due to poor visibility
- E) Time losses attributed to suboptimal material placement and visibility
- F) Shortages in materials

4. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This paper aims to scrutinize and evaluate the existing business policies, processes, and procedures of Warex India pertaining to procurement and material handling. Subsequent to this analysis, a comprehensive plan will be developed, assessed, and put into action, incorporating Lean Management (LM) principles. The central focus of implementing LM principles is to diminish the quantity of line-side stock, minimize obsolete stock, and optimize material expediting processes, thereby leading to substantial financial savings per project. The identified issues for improvement include:

- a) Improving and expediting processes at the goods receiving department to reduce lead times, incorporating the elimination of manual procedures.
- b) Implementing a Kanban system to enhance material visibility throughout the entire manufacturing process.
- c) Improving the visibility of parts stored in multiple locations.
- d) Redesigning the current facility layout to optimize material flow and visibility.
- e) Introducing a proactive alert system for non-conforming part numbers and products.
- f) Identifying part groupings to determine delivery frequencies and coordinating necessary arrangements with suppliers.
- g) Enhancing material management procedures by directly linking information to the Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system.
- h) Eliminating unnecessary on-site materials when not required.

The scope of the study extends to proposing and assessing Lean management principles that align with the evolving requirements of the ERP system currently in the design and development phase. The ultimate goal is to boost efficiency, minimize waste, and achieve seamless integration between Lean principles and the progressing ERP system at Warex India.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW

There are numerous definitions for lean Manufacturing, I will only use two different definitions and then elaborate on the concept of lean Manufacturing.

Eliminating the wastes, respecting the human workforce and Continuous improvement efforts are the key principles to go Lean. These could be practiced by 1) refining the systems, such that re-work is not required and desired information is available, 2) training the academic and non-academic workforce so that they practice lean thinking and imbibe them in their methods and procedures and 3) collaborate with peers to develop iterative procedures for continuous improvement, finally 4) and most importantly training in Lean principles and practices. (Sinha, 2013) . I was clear that the main objective was to eliminate waste in all processes to improve an organization as a whole. The waste they refer to is not just on production floor, but in reality it needs to be eliminated throughout the whole organization from Finances, Human Resources, Logistics, IT and another aspect that is clear from LM is that it has a culture. For lean management, everybody must believe in it and really pursue it from top down from management to floor workers. But it doesn't stop either, because for LM to work you also need to take your suppliers and networks into consideration and make them part of the dream as well. We need to form a long-term relationships with them to improve factors such as quality. To put more emphasis on the importance of everybody's commitment and involvement to make LM work, we developed a model of lean management as

Figure 1: LM implementation framework.

In the process Lean management to work, everybody must believe in it and really pursue it from the top down- from management to floor workers. But it doesn't stop there either, because for the Lean Management to work you also need to take your suppliers and networks into consideration and make them part of the dream as well. A long-term relationship must be formed to improve factors such as quality. To put more emphasis on the importance of everybody's commitment and involvement to make LM work. I proposed a framework in the figure 1 shows that LM has a culture and a philosophy, and that it needs everybody's participation, as well as continuing to constantly strive to improve in all aspects of the business. I previously said that LM primary focuses on eliminating waste. There are currently 8 different types of wastes identified (Redmond.J., 2008) below

1. Overproduction: Producing parts or components which there are no customer orders for, which results in unnecessary holding costs, raw materials used, labour costs etc.
2. Waiting (time on hand): Workers that are waiting for a machine to perform a task, tools or parts to be issued etc.
3. Unnecessary transport or conveyance: Refers to carrying Work -in progress (WIP) over long distance, raw materials are located in the wrong areas of a plant and needs to be moved long distances.
4. Excess Inventory: Excess raw material. WIP or finished goods causing longer lead times, obsolescence, damaged goods, transportation and storage costs.
5. Unnecessary movement: Wasted motion where workers have to look for tools or material as well as materials that are moved from one place to another unnecessary.
6. Defects: Production of defective parts or correction. Repair or rework of parts due to redesigns.
7. Unused employee creativity: losing time, employee ideas and creativity by not engaging with your employees.
8. Over processing or incorrect processing: Parts that needs to be reproduced due to wrong tooling equipment, defect parts, producing a wrong product at the wrong time.

To effectively implement LM principles, the main objective is to eliminate as much as possible of the 8 wastes described above.

5.1 PERSONNEL

Personnel and team work is just as important as any of the other aspects discussed previously. In fact, in the end it is the people and workers that add value to your company by actually manufacturing and producing finished products for sales. Laying off of personnel after long production runs or finished projects, contradicts all the characteristics of LM, long term relationships, continuous improvement, etc.

If production runs are finished, feedback sessions and redesign and configuration of the processes should be made, these should include the working personnel. They are the ones working with the products and they can give valuable information, ideas and creativity to improve processes. This is the concept in LM which is known as the culture. If you involve them in the process improvement phase, you start by creating a culture that seeks continuous improvement all over your organization. When line workers start developing and imparting the skills of resolving problems themselves, your organization will successfully become lean, in fact it will be faster than your counter competition. If your organization can successfully implement lean, an increase in market share will be evident because of reduce costs and improved quality and responsiveness.

5.2 Just in time

Just in time (JIT) is one of the most important principles of LM and is one of the many techniques a lot of companies strive to apply and archive. JIT (Monden.Y., 2011) is the successful completion of a product or service at each stage of production activity from vendor to customer just-in-time for its use and at minimum cost. The main objective and deriving force of the JIT is to reduce waste by improving the way an organization manages their inventory and apply JIT management principles. The main principles is to cut lot sizes and increase frequency of orders, cut buffer inventory, cut purchasing costs, improve materials handling, reduce inventory levels, and seek reliable suppliers. Majority of organization uses EOQ model for determining the quantity or lot size. For example, a firm might order a lot size of 40 units to produce 20 units over a production period of 2 weeks. This means the firm only produce 2 units/day or 10 units/week. This example of EOQ modelling contradicts the JIT principle because the firm will have 20 units of raw materials on their premises, which they are not going to use for another week. This increases inventory levels, reduce space capacity and increases work loads of material handlers unnecessarily. Another major concern with this model is that they are connected to Master Production Schedule (MPS) and the planning production rate over a period of set time. But it does not keep track of actual progress of MPS and production rate. If production falls behind schedule the EOQ lot size will still be ordered regardless of whether the pervious ordered raw materials for that job is actually consumed. This creates unwanted excess inventory levels. If production is in front of schedule, material shortages will be experienced. Using these examples above describes JIT at its best, because it will reduce the inventory levels, increase productivity and reduce lead times needed for materials. This is because materials will only be used when they are needed. This is achieved by applying KABAN system.

5.3 Seek Reliable suppliers

The success of LM and JIT implementation depends upon reliable supplier. This principle puts emphasis on long term relationships with the suppliers. Long term relationships with suppliers will have one of the biggest impacts on the success of any JIT implementation project. This can be achieved by creating and conducting training JIT programs for all the suppliers by experts in the company. It is important to know the capability of logistics and supply chain of the suppliers.

5.4 Communication

The moderate support for improved communication in the organization attributable to the lean implementation. (T.L, 2006). Communication between management and the worker on the floor is also crucial. It might not be verbal communication in the sense of the actual voice of the workers, but it refers to the actual production rate and the use of raw materials.

5.5 Automation

The integration of innovative automation technology in Lean Production is an up to date and promising topic. (Kolberg.D. & Zuhike.D, 2015). One of the rule in JIT and LM environment is to automate machine. This normally applies to highly tedious and repetitive work like spot welding in the automotive industry.

5.6 5S

5S basically refers to basic housekeeping rules. The term 5S is simply allocated, because it consists of 5 Japanese words all starting with a S. The 5 words and their basic meaning is described as Seiri- arrangement, Seiton- orderliness, Seiso- cleanliness, Seiketsu- clean up

,Shitsuku- discipline . By applying 5S will mean that every part/tool/ equipment will be in its allocated space in orderly and clean manner. After a shift or specified time and task, everything is cleaned and still in their right places, and this needs to be continuously applied with discipline. 5S will mainly reduce high setup costs and reduce lead times for set up cost to perform tasks. This is achieved by eliminating time operators need to look for tools/ material/ equipment to perform their tasks by applying the 5S principle.

5.7 KANBAN

Kanban can be defined as the production scheduling and inventory control card system. Kanban is a Japanese word and its meaning literally means card. Thus, a Kanban system uses plastic cards to control production scheduling and inventory levels of a production facility. The Kanban system is one of the manufacturing strategies for lean production with minimal inventory and reduced costs. (Rahman N.A, 2013). There are three types of cards that can be used:

- a. The production authorization card: This card signals that production of certain item or procedure can begin.
- b. The vendor authorization card: This card signals the vendor/store pickers to send some specific item that is needed on the line or warehouse.
- c. The conveyance authorization card: This card gives a material handler authority to move a product from one place to another location.

The supplier Ekanban is only one step on the ladder of improvement. (MacKerron, 2014) The system can also be driven by means of technology by sending messages via network servers to the applicable stages and stations. This is also known as Electronic Data Interchange (EDI). Instead of moving physical cards, messages are sent in email format to suppliers, stores etc. by using a network. This can be managed automatically with barcodes which makes the process so much quicker because the inventory levels are updated virtually in real time, which means that the time it takes to move a Kanban card to a next station is eliminated.

5.8 Integration of JIT/MRP

Material Resource Planning (MRP) uses software to help and control the use of dependent demand inventory items and schedule finished product production MRP is a program that uses the Master Production Schedule (MPS) to plan the procurement and expediting processes of raw materials needed to complete production according to MPS. This also known as Push system in LM. JIT is based on Pull system.

6. CONCEPTUAL DESIGN AND POSSIBLE SOLUTION

The paper is based on casual study on a case-study based method, where I used Warex India as case. Warex India designed a new ERP system and already purchased a barcode software module. By implementation of an integrated barcode solution with a new ERP system, company wanted to obtain better control of their materials by applying 5S and accurate routings, increase their picking accuracy, reduce queue times at various departments, increase the visibility of materials in the plant, achieve more accurate stock levels and accurate space allocations of parts. The company designed new ERP with barcode system can be utilized more by using it as an input measure of actual stock levels in the warehouse, production line and parts that needs to be painted and then sent to the desired locations/ workstation. By implementing this strategy, it acts as an Ekanban system that was in turn, also be the first phase of moving towards a JIT system. With a modification to the current part number format, a more accurate routing system was also achieved by sending the materials to the desired location in the round. Sometimes parts get booked in at Goods receiving step, then get booked into stores, and then sent from the line

to the paint shop and only then returned to the same location on the production line where the part is assembled in the vehicle.

This process was improved by implementing a new part numbering method for more advanced routing of parts. The current part number only reveals a parts identity but not its location or routing.

7. WORK APPROACH- CASE WAREX INDIA

The approach was based upon the topics and techniques discussed earlier and are broken down into the different phases as analyse process, station layout, generate product families, equipment required, cost analysis, evaluation and feasibility study of the project, conclusion, future improvement and implementation plans, final document completion.

In the first phase as define and analyse processes, the company's organization charts were obtained which was followed by workshops to identify all the role players who were involved in the processes. After all the role players were identified and assigned to all the operations and processes Techco India followed process flow charts was drawn up from the functional diagrams. The focus was on the materials management and production processes because this was where the most value have to be added by implementing LM principles. These AS-IS process include good receiving, binning and picking procedures. All the information flow between all the role plyers, procurement, material planners and suppliers were taken into account. After these processes were analysed, we focused on the requirements for Warex India to improve their current processes as well as integrating the LM. These processes were also measured against reference models that are used in industry. The company introduced the manual Kanban by incorporating the following features as track and traceability solution for materials, reduced inventory levels on site, a pull system, improved processes to control production, develop requirements for a bar code solution. A manual Kanban process was developed and implemented. From the start of a project all the components' Kanban cards are developed with all the delivery addresses and replenishment quantities. The concept is that the part can move in various combinations between multiple internal destinations. A part is sent from the warehouse to desired delivery locations, for example; the assembling process. When the integration line reaches a predetermined stock level, they will trigger the assembly shop to release certain parts on request with Kanban card. The same applies to the assembly shop, when they reach their minimum stock levels, a Kanban card will then be sent to the warehouse to replenish the stock levels. The warehouse works on the exact same principle except the Kanban card which is sent to the procurement department where the material planner and buyer communicate with the supplier via telephone or email to fill the order. Parts are delivered to the warehouse and are united with their original Kanban card. This process is looped throughout all the operations and different sections of the production floor. Since the manual Kanban was implemented, stock levels on the integration line were dramatically reduced and the visibility of material increased. A short summary is given in the Annexure 1 below of how the stock level changes where the Kanban process has been implemented. In the phase 2, after analysing the current processes it is apparent that there was a definitive need for a dedicated department to manage the station layouts and planning. In the past Techco India production demand was not as high and it was not really required. But as the demand increased it was clear that this was the necessary step which helped to control, maintain and compliment production. The required tasks identified as BOM (bill of materials) from engineering, determine the space needed for the parts per station, determine the quantity per part that needs to be in a Kanban , calculate the required amount of material, rack space and the type of materials, design the station layout , critical parts to be identified and coloured , all the sub-assemblies needed to be identified in every operation and routed to sub-assembly area. Kanban cards are required for all the parts

and the right quantity of cards is to be calculated to ensure a functional Kanban system. Under the Phase 3, using the existing BOM's all the parts have been grouped in the families and depending upon the specific property, these product families are categorised in groups. All the parts on the BOM needed to be placed in one of the above categories and depending on the specific property and physical appearance of that part, a suitable label was assigned to the part. After the labelling methods were assigned to the different products, a sample size of all the product categories was tested and evaluated and then the final decisions and assignment was made to all product types. In the evaluate equipment phase i.e. Phase 4, the requirements from the ERP vendor, wireless network, and Techco IT department regarding the scanner specifications are shown in the Annexure 2. The different types of scanners available in the market are also shown in the Annexure 2. After design of the system, scanners were allocated to the areas where they were used and the required quantities were also determined for each area. Most of the parts were marked and labelled already from suppliers. The parts that were not marked or labelled required internal marking methods. The prices for all the scanners and part marking equipment chosen are shown in the Annexure 3 along with the quantities of each scanner that was used. In phase 5, cost analysis was done. Techco India during the past 2 years produced 540 wireless equipment over 3 projects with a few smaller projects running parallel to these big projects. Of these 540 equipments, the amount of production hours lost and obsolescence stock is summarized in Annexure 4. Letters had been sent out to all Techco suppliers on a request to supply parts already bar coded. Most of the supplier confirmed and supplied marked products. Only a small amount of part was marked internally. The direct part marking Telesis machine and the labels required to mark parts internally, which were already included in the cost of equipments. Typically, a machine is assembled out of 300 parts and each parts required 6 Kanban cards. This means that on average every project must require 1800 different Kanban cards at an estimated cost of INR 1.79/cards. Total cost of using Kanban cards will amount to INR 3222 per project. Total cost of scanner is INR 236171 (from Annexure-3). Wireless network was developed by the ERP at no additional cost. A product app Bridgelogix (interface program between ERP and scanners) came along with ERP at no additional cost. The bar coding solution was the first phase of moving towards a lean Management environment and was typically reduced the queue lengths, improve productivity, material visibility and traceability. Normally a 15% to 30% improved productivity can be expected. The second phase of the project is to use all the data available from the system to start implementing pull principles, fine tuning the Ekanban system. An accurate database has been developed and in place. Some of the key data was captured pertaining to supplier lead time, waiting time, queue times as well as production time. From this data Techco India was able to calculate accurate holding costs, waiting cost as well as the impact of JIT versus their current methods. Finally, the project moved to a JIT environment and continually improved all the processes using the data from phase 2. A summary of the projected improvement percentages and savings are summarized in Annexure 5. The company is at running on 65% productivity with a net saving INR 1.39,69,480. The total cost of the project implementation is INR 2.36.171(refer annexure 6). The Monte Carlo Simulation models were used to determine the average savings that Warex India can expect over 3 years to follow. Annexure 7 shows the summary of the savings for each year. The ROI was calculated and the anticipated ROI percentage of 9% makes the project of implementing a barcode solution very promising. Any percentage above 4.67% achieved from the simulated data will return a positive ROI percentage.

8. CONCLUSION

Monte Carlo simulation data and financial findings above it is clear that this is very profitable and successful endeavour for any company because it reduce inventory levels, increase visibility and traceability of materials , improve control over materials , improve material flow patterns, increase production productivity and efficiency, reduce obsolescence stock due to increased visibility , reduce lost time due to improved material placement and visibility and reduce material shortage. The most valuable output of the case can be concluded as it will increase capacity and reduce project delay.

9. LIMITATION

The end to end process improvement after consultation with the local suppliers for the purpose of streamlining the supply chain is one of the main limitation of our study.

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ANNEXURE 1

Inventory levels Improvements with KANBAN

Operation	Stock level without Kanban (Units)	Stock level with Kanban	% Floor area saved
21	2860	858	70
50	8370	2511	70
60	4270	1704	60
70	8932	3126.2	65
90	40733	8855	78.26

ANNEXURE 2

GATES AND QUALITY SCANNERS REQUIRED

GATE	QTY	TYPE OF SCANNER
Good Receiving	1-2	MT2090
Quality Assurance	2	DS3407
Picking	2-3	MC3090
Delivery at Integration	5	DS3478
Delivery at Assembly shop	2	DS3478

ANNEXURE 3

**TOTAL COST OF BAR CODING EQUIPMENT AND
HARDWARE**

	PRICE	QTY	TOTAL
DS3407	11455	2	22910
DS3478	14382	7	100674
MT2090	19275	2	38550
MC3090	24679	3	74037
	INR		236171

ANNEXURE 4

**PRODUCTION HOURS LOST AND OBSELESCENCE STOCK
VALUES**

Project #	Production Hours Lost	Production hours value @avreage of INR100/hour	Obsolescence stock value in INR
Project 1	1364	136400	198200
Project 2	1785	178500	806555
Project 3	1414	141400	654098
Total	4563	456300	1658853

ANNEXURE5

SIMULATED AND PROJECTED SAVINGS PER PHASE

Phase	Percentage improvement between	Avg. Productivity Hours Saved per Machine in INR value	Avg. Obsolescence stock saved per Machine in INR value	Total Rands saved per Machine	Total Rands saved per year based on 100 Machines produced
1	15%- 30%	273	39640	39913	3991280
2	30%- 60%	682	99100	99782	9978200
3	65%-85%	955	138740	139695	13969480

ANNEXURE 6

TOTAL PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION COST

Equipment	Cost
Scanner and Marking Lasers	236171
Bridgelogix	N/A
Wireless Network	N/A
Total Costs	236171

ANNEXURE7

TOTAL PROJECTED SAVINGS

Year	Savings Expected
1	564427
2	733755
3	953881
Total	2252062

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